

Open-Source Software Special Reference to Libraries

Dr. Mahavir Mahadevrao Katke

Librarian, Late V.D. College, Bhabhalgaon, Dist - Latur

Corresponding author- Dr. Mahavir Mahadevrao Katke

Email: mahavirkatake@gmail.com

Abstract

The paper while giving the information to introduction of the concept, describes the open-source Software (OSS) and explains the meaning of the term OSS, Definition the OSS used to explain it and also elaborates some of the important issues with reference to the explanation of the OSS. The paper enumerates the important characteristics of the OSS and Advantage and Disadvantage It describes important OSS, being presently used worldwide with special reference to the popular OSS used in Libraries Like as Library Automation Software Ex. Koha, Newgenlib, and Evergreen.

Keywords: software's, open-source , library science

Introduction

Open-source software (OSS) is computer software with its source code available to the general public for use as is or with modification and made presented with a license in which the copyright holder provides the rights to study, change and distribute the software to anyone and for any purpose. This software classically does not require a license fee. Open-source software is unique in that it is always released under a license that has been certified to meet the criteria of the Open-source Definition. These criteria include the right

1. Redistribute the software without restriction
2. Access the source code
3. Modify the source code
4. Distribute the modified version of the software

1.2 Other Valuable Systems (Servers & Desktops)

S.No.		
1.	Apache, Mozilla's Firefox	HTTP Web Server
2.	CentOS	Linux Distribution from Red Hat's development efforts
3.	Fedora	Linux desktop system
4.	JBoss	J2EE server for Enterprise Java Development
5.	Slackware	Linux distribution

1.3 Productivity Software

S.No.		
1.	Evolution	Calendar, contact manager and e-mail client
2.	Firefox	Web browser
3.	Gimp	Image manipulation program
4.	Open Office	Word processor, spreadsheet
5.	Thundebird	e-mail client, news aggregator

1.4 Open-Source and Developers: OSS projects are group effort opportunities that get improved skills and construct connections in this field. Developers must be competent with standard tools of open – source development.

S.No.		
1.	Communication tools	Email, real-time messaging, forums, and wikis help developers to discover solutions or bound ideas offeach other.
2.	Distributed revision control system	When multiple developers in different geographical locations modify data and files, these systems supervise the different versions and updates.
3.	Bug trackers and task lists	Allow large- scale projects to monitor issues and keep track of their fixes.
4.	Testing and debugging tools	Automate testing during system integration and debug other programs

2 Advantages of Open-Source Software

In the present day, open-source software has developed into critical for approximately every organization. Approximately everything requires open-source software, be it telecommunication systems, inventory, accounting, personal productivity applications, contact management, and operating systems amongst others. Open-source software can have a most important impact on the complete organization. There are a number of advantages to using open-source software. The subsequent are a list of the advantages of opting for open-source software.

2.1 Lesser Hardware Costs

In view of the fact that Linux and open-source solutions are easily portable and compressed, it takes lesser hardware power to carry out the same tasks compared to the hardware power it takes on servers, such as Solaris, Windows, or workstations. With this less hardware power improvement, you can even use cheaper or older hardware and still get the required results.

2.2 High-Quality Software

Open-source software is mainly high-quality software. Use the open-source software, the source code is accessible. Most open-source software is well-designed. Open-source software can also be economically used in coding. These reasons make open-source software a perfect selection for organizations.

2.3 No Vendor Lock-In

IT managers in organizations face invariable irritation when dealing with vendor lock-ins. Be short of portability, expensive license fees and the inability to customize software are some of the other disadvantages. Using open-source software gives you more freedom and you can successfully address all these disadvantages.

2.4 Integrated Management

By using open-source software, you can benefit from integrated management. Open-source software uses technologies, such as the common information model (CIM) and web-based enterprise management (WBEM). These high-end technologies enable you to integrate and combine server, application, and service and workstation management. This integration would result in efficient administration.

2.5 Simple License Management

Open-source software, enables you to install it a number of times and also use it from every location. You will be free from monitoring, tracking or counting license compliance.

2.6 Lower Software Costs

Using open-source software can help you minimize your expenses. You can save on licensing fees and maintenance fees. The only expenses that you would encounter would be expenditures for documentation media and support.

2.7 Abundant Support

You will get enough support when you use open-source software. Open-source support is mainly freely available and can be without problems accessed through online communities. There are also many software companies that offer free online help and also mixed levels of paid support. Most organization that creates open-source software solutions also provides maintenance and support.

2.8 Scaling And Consolidating

Linux and open-source software can be simply scaled. With mixed options for clustering, load balancing, and open-source applications, such as email and database you can enable your organization to either scale up and achieve higher growth or consolidate and achieve more with less.

3. Disadvantages of Open-Source Software

The major disadvantage of open-source software is not being uncomplicated to use. Open-source operating systems approximating Linux cannot be learned. They necessitate effort and probably training from your side before you are able to master them. You may need to employ a trained person to make things easier, but this will incur additional costs.

3.1 Difficulty Of Use

Some open-source applications may be complicated to set up and use. Others may lack user-friendly interfaces or features that your staff may be recognizable with. This can influence productivity and put off your staff from adopting or using the programs with ease.

3.2 Compatibility Issues

Many types of proprietary hardware need particular drivers to run open-source programs, which are frequently only available from the equipment manufacturer. This can potentially add to the cost of your project. Even if an open-source driver exists, it may not work with your software as well as the proprietary driver.

3.3 Liabilities And Warranties

With proprietary software, the developer frequently provides indemnification and guarantee as part of a standard license agreement. This is because they have full control and copyright over the product and its fundamental code. Conventional open-source software licenses classically contain only limited warranty and no responsibility or infringement indemnity protection.

3.4 Hidden Costs

Software that is free up- face but later costs money to run can be a main burden, particularly if you have "t careful about these hidden costs from the outset.

4. Open-Source Software Special Reference to Libraries

5. 4.1 Library Automation

4.1.1 Koha: Integrated Library System

Koha is an open-source Integrated Library System (ILS) used world-wide by public, school and special libraries. Koha is web-based ILS, with a

SQL database (MySQL prefer) backend with cataloguing data stored in MARC and easy to get to Z39.50 or SRU. The user interface is very

configurable and adaptable and has been translated into many languages

S.No.	Koha FREE LIBRARY SYSTEM	
1.	Year	Created in 1999 by Katipo Communications for the Horowhenua Library Trust in New Zealand and the First installation went live in January 2000.
2.	Developer	Koha Community
3.	Initial release	January 2000
4.	Stable release	17.05.01/ June 23, 2017
5.	Preview release	17.05.00/ May 31, 2017
6.	Repository	Github.com/koha-Community/Koha
7.	Written in	Perl
8.	Operating System	Linux
9.	Type	Integrated Library System
10.	License	GNU General Public License V3
11.	Website	Koha-community.org

4.1.2 NewGenLib : New Generation Library

NewGenLib is an outcome of collaboration between Verus and Kesavan Institute of Information and Knowledge management. NGL is developed and maintained by Verus Solutions and Kesavan Institute has provided the domain expertise. NewGenLib is an integrated library management system developed by Verus Solutions Pvt Ltd. Domain knowledge is provided by Kesavan Institute of Information and Knowledge Management in Hyderabad, India.

NewGenLib version 1.0 was released in March 2005. On 9 January 2008, NewGenLib was declared free and open-source under GNU GPL. The Latest version of NewGenLib is 3.1.1 released on 16 April 2015. Many Libraries across the globe (mainly from the developing countries) are using NewGenLib as their Primary Integrated Library Management System as seen from the NewGenlib discussion forum.

S.No.	NewGenLib FREE LIBRARY SYSTEM	
1.	Year	2005
2.	Original Author	Siddhartha Errabolu and L.J. Haravu
3.	Developer	Verus Solutions
4.	Initial release	March 2005
5.	Written in	Java
6.	Operating System	Linux, Windows
7.	Type	Integrated Library System
8.	License	GNU General Public License V
9.	Website	Verussolutions.biz

4.1.3 Evergreen: Evergreen is an open-source Integrated Library System (ILS) initially developed by the Georgia Public Library Service for Public Information Network for Electronic Services (PINES) a state-wide resource sharing consortium with over 270 member libraries. PINES the Evergreen ILS is deployed worldwide in approximately

1800 libraries and is used to power a number of state-wide consortial catalogs. In 2007 the original Evergreen development team software Equinox Software which provides custom support development migration training and consultation for Evergreen.

S.No.	Evergreen (Software)	
1.	Year	2006
2.	Developer	Georgia Public Library Service (GPLS) Public Information Network for Electronic Services (PINES) and the Evergreen Community
3.	Initial release	September 2006
4.	Repository	Git.evergreen-ils.org/Evergreen.git
5.	Written in	C, Perl, XUL, JS
6.	Operating System	Linux
7.	Platform	Cross-Platform
8.	Available	English
9.	Type	Integrated Library System
10.	License	GNU General Public License
11.	Website	Evergreen-lis.org

Conclusion: Evaluation of open-source software is different from proprietary programs. A key difference for evaluation is that the information available for open-source programs is usually different than for proprietary programs; source code, analysis by others of the program design, and discussion between users and developers on how well it is working. Often proprietary programs always hide all information from users and only allow running the software.

That there are some very controlling solutions presented today that could be used to create a much more resourceful library. By using open-source software in the library money that otherwise would be spent on software solutions can be used for other important resources, such as purchasing additional media resources (books, journals) or can be used to appoint educated technical support that provides customers with the know how to better use already existing resources. This free software is constantly being updated, changed and customized to meet the library's needs. While all of this is fine and dandy and sounds like the win-win solution for your library there are still pitfalls and hurdles we all need to overcome.

Reference:

1. <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open-sour>
Accessed on 15.07.17
2. www.neteasy.us Accessed on 19.07.17
3. www.thebalance.com Accessed on 19.07.17
4. <http://www.outsource2india.com> Accessed on 19.07.17
5. <http://cloudtweaks.com> Accessed on 19.07.17
6. www.Nibusinessinfo.co.uk Accessed on 19.07.17
7. [http://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Koha_\(software\)](http://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Koha_(software)) Accessed on 22.07.17
8. www.verussolutions.biz/web/ Accessed on 19.07.17
9. <http://en.m.wikipedia.org>wik>New...>
Accessed on 22.07.17
10. <https://en.m.wikipedia.org>wiki>Everg...>
Accessed on 23 .07.17
11. Witten, Ian H. & Bainbridge, D. (2007). A retrospective look at Greenstone: Lessons from the first decade. *JCDL '07,2007* 147-156.
12. [http://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Greenstone_\(software\)](http://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Greenstone_(software)) Accessed on 28.07.17